

Background

- Native to Australia, Southeast Asia and Pacific archipelagos, comprises about 15 species.
- Moved extensively around the world by humans.
- Major ecological, economic and cultural value worldwide.
- Some species are deemed undesirable.

Figure 1. (a) Mining rehabilitation. (b) Dune stabilisation and shade. (c) Spectacular invasion on Réunion Island, France. (d) Extensive plantations in China.

Methods

We searched the literature and surveyed databases and extracted information on the:

- introduction history and current distribution of taxa,
- status as alien species,
- economic importance,
- impacts of invasions on ecosystems,
- evolution of management strategies.

Global distributions were mapped, representation in bioclimatic zones examined and potential global distribution modelled.

Results

- Introduced to nearly 100 countries.
- 3 species with greatest distribution:
 - *Casuarina equisetifolia* – in 90 countries,
 - *Casuarina cunninghamiana* – in 47 countries,
 - *Casuarina glauca* – in 23 countries.
- Naturalised/invasive in 35 countries
- Cause various economic and environmental impacts.

Results (continued)

- 8 % of the Earth's land surface is potentially suitable for casuarinas.
- Number of countries in which naturalisation is evident, varies between climatic suitability.

Figure 2. Diversity of *Casuarina* species world-wide at a 15° scale.

Results (continued)

- Large-scale plantings in some climatically suitable areas have yet to result in large-scale invasions.
- The species which are invasive have the largest native ranges.

Figure 3. Relationship between native and naturalized range sizes.

Conclusion

- Distinct phylogenetic lineage and native biogeography provides an important supplementary test of the generalities of invasion.